

Neurospicy Libraries

Report 1: Workplace Environment

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Introduction

This report details the findings of the first survey conducted as part of the Neurospicy Libraries project. This project has involved several activities, one of which is surveying people within a peer support network of neurodivergent library employees across three different areas of difficulty in the workplace.

This first survey and report focuses on the workplace environment in terms of physical issues that might impact on sensory sensitivities or physical disabilities associated with neurodivergency, but also navigating the unwritten rules of the social and cultural workplace environment. This was identified as the most important area of concern in an initial survey which asked about different potential areas of focus.

The focus of these reports is not to go through a full objective research process with shared data, comprehensive literature reviews and systematic analysis. The approach is much more informal, and can be thought of as a collection of anonymous lived experiences that are communicated through the Neurospicy Project leads who are acting as 'cover' for the respondents who engaged. Participants would not necessarily disclose their neurodivergence publicly or even within a closed workplace, and even further than this would not submit responses of this nature to a formal research project even if anonymity was offered and prefer to offer information to grass roots, practicality focussed projects lead by peers only. Responses do however act as evidence to support communication from the Neurospicy Libraries project leads – this is not just us, this is the voice of many individuals working in libraries now who are struggling in private.

There were 91 respondents to this survey

Respondents are all self identified neurodivergent individuals working in libraries in the UK, and while the project is affiliated with academic libraries north, they do include individuals working in other areas of the UK and other library sectors outside of academic settings.

Participants were asked to respond to a range of free text questions via Google Forms, and were not asked about any contextual information beyond how they would describe their neurodivergency. All responses were anonymous. Participants were not asked about data sharing beforehand and so the full responses are not available to be shared.

Questions

1. What problems, difficulties or issues do you encounter in the physical workplace environment?
2. What do you do personally to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues in the physical workplace environment?
3. What mitigations does your workplace put in place to help with any problems, difficulties or issues in the physical workplace environment?
4. What problems, difficulties or issues do you encounter in the cultural workplace environment?
5. What do you do personally to overcome these problems, difficulties or issues in the cultural workplace environment?
6. What mitigations does your workplace put in place to help with any problems, difficulties or issues in the cultural workplace environment?
7. What would the hypothetical "perfect" workplace environment, physical and cultural, be like for you?
8. Is there anything else you'd like to add about the workplace environment?

How would you describe your own neurodivergence? Tick as many as apply, formal diagnoses not required.

91 responses

The biggest two categories were Autism and ADD/ADHD, but this masked a large range of co-existing conditions – 33 out of the 91 (36%) respondents selected more than one type of neurodivergence. *(Therefore, often hard to unpick between different things)*

Literature Review and Analysis

No formal literature review or analysis methodology has been formulated. Responses were read through in full and the most common themes collated in a subjective manner, with example responses that convey the essence of that theme offered. They are then linked to the most salient advice available across a range of resources and guides in a similarly informal manner.

Results

Workplace environment – physical

A = distractions (54/91). General distractions, lots of overlap between issues around noise, light, etc., but often around just having any noise (for example), rather than the volume. This is a major category, with 59% respondents mentioning one or more distractions that made work more difficult. More if we include those who mentioned noise but didn't explicitly mention that noise was an issue because it was distracting.

Typical quotes:

"Open office, too many distractions..."

"...my colleague has to come in and out regularly which disturbs me when I'm focusing..."

"Getting distracted by chatter and general noise in the open plan office."

"I get distracted by sounds, chat around me and notifications of some sort."

"I find noise and distractions hard to deal with."

"Interruptions from colleagues disrupting the flow of a job resulting in mid-task paralysis."

B= Temp (12/91) – too hot / cold.

Typical quotes:

"I have sensory issues so temperature regulation and noise/light tolerance can be an issue..."

"Too cold or too hot."

"...temperature levels often fluctuate to uncomfortable levels (too hot or too cold)..."

C = Equipment issues (6/91) of various sorts, from uncomfortable headsets, to screens, to desk space

"Furniture - doesn't fit how I sit to work."

"white table tops as standard"

"I have to wear a wired headset with a microphone for calls which I find uncomfortable and restrictive."

D = Lighting (22/91) – often lights being too bright or harsh

"Lighting - fluorescent tubes on a low ceiling and very limited natural light which makes it a very stark and harsh environment. Walls are bright white along with bright accent walls. Feels like the lights are pressing down on my head"

"Lights too bright."

"Very bright overhead lighting"

E = Noise (48/91) – there is lots of overlap with (A, distractions), but also the volume of noise. 15 people mentioned noise as an issue without explicitly mentioning it being distracting – if we assumed that this was part of it, distractions (A) would go up to 69/91, or 76% of respondents.

"I struggle with random, sudden and interrupting noises"

"...too noisy and can be overwhelming at times."

"Noise levels in student areas overwhelming"

F = Wayfinding (4/91), finding their way to other locations, particularly spaces new to them (Note – is this a particular grouping – check dyspraxics?)

"New buildings with confusing layouts and no signage."

"...getting lost in libraries..."

"I struggle to locate things if they're not in the right place or they're not as described, and the potential for me to get lost on campus is higher as I have no sense of direction or space."

G = Various Hotdesking issues (10/91) – Part of this is about having suitable equipment, but it's often about disrupting coping mechanisms, whether that's knowing who will be near you, having manual planning systems (e.g. post-its), or generally disrupting routines.

"I hate this (hotdesking) as I really want to sit at the same desk each day and know where my things are and who will be next to me."

"Hot desking means facing change every day and is difficult"

"We also have a 'Hot-desking' situation so there is a 'clear desk' policy and everything must be locked away each day in a pedestal. Mine is full to busting with 'useful stuff' and I am late leaving every day because of the time it takes me to get everything put away"

H = Reading work material, etc (3/91) – these all varied, from reading spines on books, to posters / instructions, to interpreting plans / maps to guide users.

“Reading signs, posters and displays can be tricky.”

I = Comms (3/91) – this is very broadbrush and was partly about clear instructions and signage, which ND people feel they sometimes mis-interpret when NT people do not. Slightly different to (I) in that the reading of materials weren’t necessarily mentioned, but it’s more about misinterpreting.

“I sometimes discover that I have misunderstood someone’s information or instructions, or I have not communicated mine to them in a way they understand when I thought I was being clear.”

J = Fixed space (4/91) – the opposite to Hotdesking! This seemed largely to be an issue around needing different spaces which weren’t available. Space to concentrate, or decompress for instance.

“Not enough variety of seating.”

“Lack of quiet space when I need to recharge.”

K = Unforgiving space for the clumsy (4/91) – comments such as desks with sharp corners and unforgiving stairs cropped up in this category, workers who may describe themselves as clumsy and bumping into things regularly struggling in tight, often unforgiving spaces. All but one of these were dyspraxic, which isn’t surprising.

“It can be quite tight and small spaces for work which leads to me having lots of clumsy moments”

People tried to find ways around these issues, with limited success, including several people just trying to “put up” with problems.

By far the most popular mitigation was to use earbuds or headphones of some sort – some just to reduce external noise, some to play music over to drown out external noise.

Wherever possible, people tended to try and work from home wherever possible, including one respondent describing how they needed to work unpaid overtime at home to complete tasks they couldn’t manage in the normal office. Several people also described how they looked for quiet space they could book to work in outside the normal office, even if that was just for short periods. There was a strong sense amongst some respondents of needing similar spaces to escape and “reset” or decompress after being in an open plan office – going for walks around the building, or hiding in the toilets until they feel able to go back into the shared spaces.

The issue of hotdesking was partly coped with by trying to work from home or to “escape” for short periods, but people also tried to negotiate their own desk in a hotdesking environment, which wasn’t always completely successful. Talking to colleagues and managers openly about issues as a ND worker was seen as helpful in these sort of negotiations.

Assistive equipment was mentioned by a small number of people, from software to using post-its for organisation. *(This is interesting, because it’s often the main focus of disability training at my workplace!)*

Temperature issues were partially overcome by clothing options (mentions of layers or spare clothes), but hot drinks were also mentioned.

Several people mentioned switching lights off, but this often isn't possible with so many in shared spaces.

Finally there were individual comments about how people coped, like pre-preparing for social interactions, or exercising before work.

Employer mitigations were incredibly limited – 57% reported none at all, though often none had been requested, or even neurodivergence reported. Headphones (sometimes just permitting people to wear their own headphones!) were most common, but not always suitable ones *“They have given me a fairly cheap pair of ear defenders but I feel a bit awkward about wearing them in a public space. They're also not very comfortable or effective.”*

Several respondents stated that the employers couldn't do much because of restrictions imposed by existing buildings or other departments (e.g Estates), *“Not much due to the age of the building, and costs involved and concern that less light will affect other staff and students.”*

Those people who had discussed it with their managers sometimes found them very supportive and able to put minor mitigations in place (particularly being more flexible with an element of homeworking), but others found their workplaces non-responsive and unwilling to put mitigations in place. *“None. If anything, making them worse by insisting on a set % of time in the physical workplace, regardless of any actual need - it was great during peak pandemic being able to work from home all week!”*

One respondent summed up employers general approach to putting mitigations in place as: *“Despite claiming to care about EDI, neurodivergence is not taken seriously or accommodated at all really.”*

Workplace environment - cultural

The responses to this question varied a lot more than those about the physical environment, to the extent that it's hard to neatly categorise them. Some major ones, however, are:

Lack of understanding about neurodiversity. This could be with colleagues, but was often referring to managers, where others were seen as lacking in understanding of neurodivergence, or even dismissive of it completely. Sometimes this is quite explicit (*“Lack of understanding of neurodivergence, poor implementation of management techniques, processes can be hostile to ND behaviours”*), sometimes implied by the sense that the ND individual should just cope with things as they are (*“...assuming that because I'm an older adult, I can cope.”*; *“I've been told I'm giving in to Autism...”*) It isn't the same as lack of training and awareness raising, but more a lack of acceptance, as though ND people just need to try harder to be “normal”.

Rules, including unwritten ones are a significant area of concern for our respondents. Following the rules when neurotypical people may seem not to (*“It always feels like everyone is playing a different game to me.”*), or misinterpreting rules especially around social interactions (*“In the past I have 'said the wrong thing' at work a lot and withdrew from small talk which meant relationships suffered and my progression and reputation suffered with it.”*). Rules, deadlines and tasks could be seen as unclear and hard for ND workers to interpret (*“Imprecise and ambiguous language; inability of colleagues to give precise deadlines, and to indicate priorities”*).

A strong sense of fairness was often seen as an issue as NT people didn't seem to share this. Respondents described how they struggled with this, pushing for resolutions that others didn't seem to be interested in (*"Struggle with 'unfairness', which means I'm sometimes seen as awkward, or problematic as I want to make sure that people are equitably dealt with."*)

Struggling with conventional deference to authority which is a typical ND trait and one which people struggled with in their workplaces, nicely summed up by one person as *"unable to tolerate pointless hierarchy"* which can be difficult both for the ND worker and the NT managers. (*"...the hierarchy and the constant need to follow the rules without any clear explanation of why the rules are in place"*.)

Several issues were raised about particular settings, particularly *interviews*, which were seen as difficult to decode and to perform well at. (e.g. *"Recruitment tends to want to ask questions that are unclear and need decoding as to what specification point they are referring to which can lead to overwhelm in face to face situations."*)

Engagement could be a difficulty for some, where the task wasn't interesting enough to hold attention, seemed to be unfair to a group, or instructions couldn't be clearly decoded (*"...if it's not interesting enough its very hard to engage with it and do a good job."*)

This point often wasn't clearly expressed, but there was an undercurrent of feeling expressed that *"socially acceptable"* and *Neurotypical people were valued over ND ones*. (*"preference for in-person meetings"; "neurodivergent team members are not supported enough in their work or valued"; "...expectation that if you're not working out loud, you're not really working"*.)

Supporting Resources

1. [Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development Guidance](#)

Many aspects of the typical working environment can act as barriers that prevent neurodivergent employees – particularly those with acute sensory sensitivity – from performing at their best at work.

Common issues to consider include:

Office lighting: bright office lights can be distracting and can contribute to sensory overload. Neurodivergent employees could be given a workspace away from such lighting, and with more natural light.

Noise levels: noisy open plan environments can also be highly distracting. HR can assign neurodivergent employees a desk in a quieter area or even a private office, and allow the use of headphones or earplugs.

Equipment: computer screens can be too bright and desks may lack items to aid personal organisation, such as trays and filing drawers. Some companies are making common equipment such as tablet computers with self-organisation apps and desk filing trays available on demand. Equipment such as photocopiers should have visible instructions nearby, as this is likely to be helpful to individuals with dyspraxia – and, as so often, for all employees

Accommodations are often simple, cheap or even free, and can make a huge difference to someone's quality of working life and ability to reach their potential. As with all employees, it's important not to assume that everyone will have the same preferences regarding workspaces, or indeed, where they work or at what times of day. Thus, overall adjustments to the workplace can be made proactively – driven by data from onboarding workspace preference questionnaires, and comfort-at-work surveys – with further adjustments available and offered to suit specific, individual preferences.

'Ahead of an office move to a city centre location, we're factoring neurodiversity considerations into the accessible design of the building. We've designed an audit checklist which helps us consider the different sensory aspects of an office space. For example, if we think about hearing, what are the sources of noise, and if we think about touch, what fabrics are being used in the office?

'We recognise that wholesale changes may not always be possible and that capital funding is tight, so we also integrate the audit checklist into the maintenance schedule. That means when you're upgrading things you can make the necessary changes then. The checklist can also be used to help inform discussions with people who may be struggling with their current work environment to prompt possible solutions.'

Sean Gilroy, Head of Cognitive Design, BBC Design and Engineering

2. [Association of Graduate Careers Advisory Services Guidance](#)

Challenge: Social interaction and communication

Examples of reasonable adjustments:

- Ask for an office mentor – maybe line manager, colleague, buddy arrangement. Someone who can help you build awareness of how you communicate and any other issues with social cues. They can help defuse difficult social situations before they become too large.

- Asking for breaks from the office can help control heightened emotion and avoid outbursts.
- Understanding that your eye contact, speech, and body language may not be the same as other co-workers.
- Ask for clear and specific information and instructions about what is expected of you e.g. when going for interviews, completing work tasks etc. This could include travel directions, photographs of people you will be meeting, when activities will start and end.
- Understanding that you may find hypothetical or abstract questions difficult and that you may also interpret language quite literally.
- Ask if the employer can avoid asking questions that are too open e.g. "Tell me a bit about yourself".
- Let employers know if you have a tendency to talk too much or focus on one particular topic at length, and that it is okay for them to let you know when you are doing this.
- Let the employer know that they may need to prompt you and ask supplementary questions in order to get the information from you that they need.
- For job interviews, invite a supporter along to help you, in case questions need to be rephrased, or you have misunderstood the context and need to be prompted. This person can act as a go-between to ease communication between you and the interviewer.
- Ask for a work trial so that you can demonstrate exactly how you would perform in the workplace. Some employers find that a two-way placement evaluation - a period of work experience - is a better way of assessing individuals' talents than a formal interview.
- A first day at work could start with a full induction, an introduction to each employee, a map of the building/office and where each person sits and a timetable for the first week.
- Ask for an explanation of any unwritten rules of the workplace.

3. [Archived copy of ACAS guidance](#)

The working environment is full of potential distractions and other obstacles that can affect performance. Some employees may be happy working in a busy and noisy environment, but others can find it impossible to focus. While an unsuitable working environment can affect the performance of all staff, it can be a particular issue for neurodivergent employees. For example, ADHD and autistic employees can be particularly sensitive to sensory inputs, such as sounds, sights and smells.

Employers can reduce many of the distractions and obstacles in the workplace by:

- redesigning the workplace to take account of the different sensory needs of staff (for example, limiting the amount of information/bright artwork displayed on walls)
- putting up dividers in appropriate areas to block and reduce noise
- having dedicated quiet areas
- allowing staff to book meeting rooms for tasks that require a lot of concentration
- providing visible instructions next to office equipment and machinery, such as photocopiers
- allocating work areas with more natural light to staff that struggle with office lighting or allowing daylight lamps
- offering flexible working arrangements such as homeworking for part of the week or allowing staff to start earlier or finish later
- providing staff with organisers, lockers, cabinets and name labels to help them organise and retain their work and equipment
- regularly reminding staff to be mindful of their colleagues and keeping noise to a minimum
- allowing employees (when appropriate) to use equipment such as noise cancelling headphones

4. [Autism Hampshire Guidance](#)

Here are some suggestions for possible adjustments to the workplace to make it more autism-friendly:

- clear and logical rules and expectations
- a relaxation space in the workplace: e.g. a quiet room
- reduction in sensory distraction/overload in the workplace: e.g. maximise natural light, enable easy control of light and temperature, reduce strong smells
- information about autism, and about support services, available so that all workers can access it
- training for managers and others about autism, including recognising autistic positives and skills
- all instructions and policies to be written and communicated clearly and accurately
- tools to assist personal work organisation, for example visual timetables, organiser apps
- that only objective criteria are used for assessment/promotion
- that work schedules are adhered to
- inclusion of autism in harassment and bullying policies, to minimise harassment and bullying of autistic workers and so that managers or employees who bully or discriminate against autistic workers are dealt with appropriately.

Reasonable adjustments for individual autistic workers might include:

- paid time off when needed
- fixed hours rather than variable shifts
- reducing specific sensory stimuli in the workplace, e.g. locating that individual's workstation in a quieter or less bright part of the office
- change of work location, for example to be nearer home, or nearer support facilities, or to a work location which is quieter or less over-stimulating
- extra breaks to enable relaxation
- providing a mentor
- individual support where schedules are unavoidably disrupted and when changes are introduced
- adjustment to the way in which assessments are carried out
- a clear routine and work schedule
- a personal workstation (rather than sharing a workstation or 'hot-desking')
- relaxation of triggers for disciplinary action for matters such as sickness absence or mistakes arising from executive function impairment
- additional training time off for treatment/appointments, as part of a policy for disability leave
- re-allocating some work to colleagues, with their agreement.

Access To Work funding may be available for some of these measures.

5. [ADHD Foundation Guidance](#)

Modifications to the work environment

- Visual prompts – e.g. wall charts for routines, checklists, post-it notes for reminders
- Physical reminders – e.g. laying out everything needed for tomorrow at the end of today, labeled 'homes' for storing tools
- Larger computer screens so everything is visible (reduces burden on memory)
- Visible clocks, allowing / encouraging use of alarms and timers

- Reducing distractions: – Allow headphones with music or ambient noise, or ear plugs – Own space if possible, with reduced level of distraction

6. Awareness Leaflets

[How to Get the Best Out of Your Autistic Employee](#)
[Autism Communication Tips](#)

Conclusion and Recommendations

What is evident from the results is that every neurodivergent employee is different and it's very important to not make assumptions on how the neurodivergence presents in an individual when planning the workplace environment. Also important to consider is that accommodations by design, rather than on request, are always better and can benefit neurotypical staff as well, for example, sound proofed meeting rooms.

This inherently makes this area very complicated – on the one hand you can't presume an accommodation will help, and on the other you are also better off planning in advance without asking. This is probably why there is no comprehensive list of suggested accommodations available to choose from or to use as suggestions. However, this could look something like thorough consideration of possibilities at the planning stage and an openness and flexibility at the individual request stage.

While many respondents to these surveys say their employer does not put in place any mitigations, generally this is due to not wanting to disclose or not knowing what to ask for, however at several points in this particular survey participants said they had disclosed and asked and were refused.

Neurodivergent staff are already within current teams, and as this report highlights, are not revealing this. Many respondents said that they did not know what to ask for and did not want to disclose difficulty, and this report has the potential to inform and empower newly instigated conversations in this area, and to enable neurodivergent staff to make changes that will increase their performance.

While not a full research study, the above report is comprehensive, and perhaps offers a better understanding of practical solutions with lived experience and summarised evidence to enable leaders and managers to support neurodivergent talent in teams, particularly library teams. Implementing appropriate suggestions from this report and increasing understanding through absorbing the information within it will hopefully lead to the unlocking of skills and talent within existing teams, increasing efficiency and impact.

To engage further with Neurospicy Libraries:

Website

<https://neurospicylibraries.wordpress.com/>

Forum

<https://neurospicylibraries.flarum.cloud/>

